

WAYS TO MODERNIZE THE MECHANISM OF MANAGEMENT OF LIGHT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

Izzatullayeva Madinabonu Yolqin qizi

Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics, 70411201-2nd-Level Master's
Student, Majoring in Management (by Industries and Sectors), Uzbekistan

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi rivojlanayotgan innovatsiyalar zamonida yengil sanoat korxonalarini innovatsion boshqarishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlarini o'rganish va ularning asosiy kamchiliklarini bartaraf etish yo'llarini aniqlash, yengil sanoat korxonalarida modernizatsiyalashtirishni keng yo'lga qo'yishdan iboratdir.

Annotation: the main purpose of this article is to study the theoretical and practical aspects of innovative management of light industrial enterprises in the era of developing innovations and identify ways to eliminate their main shortcomings, to make modernization in light industrial enterprises widespread.

Key words: light industry, transformed, modernize, globalization, external factors, leader's achievement, inextricably, implementation, Human Resource Management.

With the independence of our country, light industry enterprises have risen to a new level of quality. According to the decision of the Republican government, almost all enterprises in the network were transformed into various joint-stock companies and other forms of ownership in accordance with the nationalization program. Currently, Uzbekistan's light industry is a multi-disciplinary industrial complex, which includes cotton refineries, textiles, knitwear, sawmills, silk weaving, tailoring, Coon-shoes, tapestry, porcelain-faience ware, etc.

An important role today is played by the processes of strategic management of enterprises in the context of changes taking place on a global scale and the globalization of Within the framework of Decree No. 60 of the president of the Republic of

Uzbekistan on “development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” approved on January 28, 2022, it was noted new goals for improving ways to reform and improve the efficiency of management processes of enterprises using modern experience, as well as developing programs for economic and social development.

By ensuring stable high growth rates in the sectors of the economy, it is envisaged to increase the gross domestic product per capita — 1.6 times in the next five years and the per capita income by 2030 to US \$ 4,000, as well as to provide a basis for entering the ranks of “countries with above-average income”.

Continuing the industrial policy aimed at ensuring the stability of the national economy and increasing the share of industry in the gross domestic product, increasing the volume of production of industrial products by 1.4 times:the world economy, the development of economic ties taking place between the countries of the world, changes taking place in the financial market. It is known that today it is necessary for enterprises to be able to fight against the influence of internal and external factors, quickly adapt, have their place in the competitive struggle and win this struggle. In this competitive struggle, industrial enterprises can only achieve the goal that they set themselves by improving the activities of the enterprise.

The light industry sector of Uzbekistan plays an important role in the socio-economic development of our country. As a result of ensuring sustainable economic growth, increasing revenues from exports, prioritizing small business and private entrepreneurship, the industrial sector is the basis for social distress, i.e. ensuring employment, increasing income and, on the basis of this, increasing the way of living the population.

Today, the industrial sector in our country is distinguished not only as a highly developing sector, but also by the fact that it is steadily increasing exports, attracting foreign investment widely, and modernizing and radically updating production processes, attracting new technical and technological processes. Today, there are more than 350 thousand enterprises operating in different industries and directions, in different forms of ownership, of which almost 290 thousand are small business and light industrial enterprises. The main objective of these enterprises is to take their place

in the market and meet the needs of consumers, to take their place in foreign markets with competitive products.

And in this, an important place is occupied by how the leader sets out the management process in order for the management of industrial enterprises to reach the optimal level. Any industrial enterprise has its own management point of view.

Various processes, norms, solutions in internal departments and divisions in industrial enterprises have a direct impact on the management apparatus, such as acceptance, modern communication and organization of work in shifts. The main place in this process is occupied by technologies, employees, organizational culture, production management, finance management, management of individuals, management according to the quality of the leader's achievement of optimality.

The processes of successful and optimal management of industrial enterprises are largely dependent on external factors, in addition to internal variables. Enterprises are required to take into account and adapt to rapid changes in the external environment. Changes in the external environment necessitate the implementation of changes within the organization.

One of the important management methods in industrial enterprises, shareholder societies, firms is a business plan. Through a business plan, an inextricably linked system of management of economic processes with the aim of one goal in the interests of the whole country is created. The main tasks solved by the means of a business plan are as follows::

- description of directions and ways to implement goals for the development of the economy,
- ensuring stable, optimal growth of the economy, distribution and redistribution of material labor and financial resources between sectors and producers,
- ensuring the introduction of the achievements of the development of Science and technology; inter-sectoral integration, specialization within networks and modernization of cooperation of industrial enterprises;
- rapid regulation of the activities of economic entities and their improvement.

Through well-thought - out business strategies, it is possible to foresee the situation of industrial enterprises and analyze the network in depth, as well as to approach entrepreneurship with enthusiasm, the implementation of the strategy into successful practice is the motivation of the head of the enterprise to motivate people, satisfy their needs, and ensure their implementation in the implementation of the main types.

In conclusion, it is necessary to implement modern approaches to the management of light industry enterprises and make the most of new technologies in the production process. The leader, on the other hand, should implement carefully thought-out strategies in Human Resource Management in every possible way.

References:

1. Kamenitser, S.E. Sanoat ishlab chiqarishini boshqarish asoslari / SE Kamenitser. - M.:Fikr, 1971 yil.
2. Bobrov, O.M. Ijtimoiy ishlab chiqarishni boshqarish funktsiyalari tasniflarini takomillashtirishning ayrim masalalari / Ishlab chiqarish samaradorligining iqtisodiy muammolari. - Kiev: KINH, 1975. - No 12.
3. <https://lex.uz/docs/-5841063#-5843873>.
4. Baykov, N. Ishlab chiqarishni boshqarishni tashkil etish va samaradorligi / N. Baikov, F.Rusinov. - M.: Moskva ishchisi, 1973 yil.